

Synthesis and Structural Studies of Bis(benzoyl-*m*-nitroacetanilido)dioxomolybdenum(VI) Complex

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A mononuclear bis(benzoyl-*m*-nitroacetanilido)dioxomolybdenum(vi) complex has been synthesised and its structure elucidated by various physical methods and spectral analyses.

Bidentate β -ketoanilides in which the donor atoms are oxygen, have been extensively investigated as solid analytical reagents, since many hard metal ions are known for quantitative formation of six-membered resonance stabilised chelates with definite stoichiometry¹. Vitert *et al.*² observed that β -ketones with two aromatic rings as end-groups form more stable chelates than those with aliphatic end-groups for compounds with comparable pK_a values. In continuation of our efforts^{3,4}, benzoyl-*m*-nitroacetanilide (BNA) has been chosen which was first synthesised and used by Das⁵ and subsequently used by Syamal⁶ for the formation of molybdenum complex. Synthesis of a yellow coloured mononuclear bis(benzoyl-*m*-nitroacetanilido)dioxo complex of molybdenum(vi), $\text{MoO}_2(\text{BNA})_2$ from aqueous medium is reported. The structure has been confirmed by ir, ¹H nmr and mass spectra, X-ray powder diffraction, polarography and thermal studies.

Results and Discussion

Elemental analysis of the yellow coloured complex conform to $\text{MoO}_2(\text{BNA})_2$ and its thermal studies indicate that the first and final decomposition points are 140° and 500° respectively. The horizontal plateau at 500–680° reflects the presence of MoO_3 but at about 680° the volatilisation of the solid and thereby solid to vapour phase transition of MoO_3 starts. At a temperature of 795° the thermogram represents the yellow

liquid authenticated by the only endotherm in the DTA curve. The DTA curve showed three distinct exothermic peaks at 269, 356 and 481°. Among the three peaks, the first one being the most sharp and strongest one, stands for the obvious oxidative thermal degradation of the chelate in static air.

The electronic spectra of the ethanolic solution of BNA and $\text{MoO}_2(\text{BNA})_2$ (in ethanol) were compared with those of acetylacetone (AcAc), acetoacetanilide (AA) and the molybdenum complex of acetoacetanilide³, $\text{MoO}_2(\text{AA})_2$. The λ_{max} of acetylacetone at 278 nm is shifted towards

Fig. 1. Absorption spectra in ethanol.

the high energy region (244 nm) in acetoacetanilide (Fig. 1) which clearly indicates a change in the electronic structure. On the other hand, the reagent BNA gives, in addition to the peak at 244 nm, a broad peak at about 320 nm.

Both the peaks remain unaffected after complexing with oxomolybdenum ion.

The X-ray powder diffraction pattern of the yellow complex does not indicate any well defined pattern of the complex. The most intense line is at 11.05 Å. It indicates a preferential orientation of this plane corresponding to this interplanar spacing. Another line appearing at 5.07 Å is equally intense. The number of peaks in the MoO₂(BNA)₂ is three times greater than the reported MoO₂(AA)₂ complex.

From the polarograms of ligands AA, BNA and their oxomolybdenum complexes (in DMF-H₂O (80 : 20); concn. 10⁻²-10⁻³ M; 0.1 M KCl as supporting electrolyte), it was confirmed that the number of electrons (*n*) involved in the reduction of the compounds was unity in all

Fig. 2. $-E$ vs $\log (i_d-i)/i$.

cases. It was evident that $E_{1/2}$ shifted to more negative potentials, from ligands to metal chelates (Fig. 2), showing complex formation⁷ by ligand as well as with the stable oxomolybdate ions. The limiting currents of all the polarograms were found to be diffusion-controlled and exhibited one peak. However, the polarograms of both BNA and its corresponding complex gave separate maxima, representing the presence of nitro groups in each case. Besides, in all cases, a single well-defined cathodic wave was obtained.

The ¹H nmr spectrum (CDCl₃) of the ligand BNA suggests the presence of two forms 1 and 2, in the ratio 3 : 1. This would confirm

the occurrence of the keto-enol tautomerism in solvent medium for BNA unlike the parent ligand acetoacetanilide, which exists in the keto form only³.

Thus the ¹H nmr spectrum of BNA shows a very sharp two-proton singlet at δ 4.16, assigned to the methylene protons, flanked between two carbonyl functions in 1, and a sharp singlet at δ 5.9 with relatively low intensity assigned to the olefinic proton in 2. The relative intensities of the two types of protons were calculated to be in the ratio 3 : 1. The CONH protons in both the structures, as expected, exhibited a broad signal at δ 8.6. All the aromatic protons appeared in the region δ 7.33-8.00 as multiplets.

The ¹H nmr spectrum (DMSO-d₆ + CDCl₃) of the molybdenum complex, MoO₂(BNA)₂ was also in good agreement with structure 3. The appearance of all peaks (a broad band at δ 8.70 for NH and a multiplet at δ 7.65-8.20 for ArH), are in conformity with those of the ligand itself, excepting the slight down-field shift of the olefinic proton (appeared at δ 6.05 as a sharp singlet), in the spectrum of the molybdenum complex in comparison to the ligand³.

The EI mass spectrum of the complex **3** (proposed ion reaction shown in Scheme 1), showed no metal containing peak, but instead gave a peak in the highest mass region at m/z 284. This peak corresponds to the ligand molecule. The non-appearance of the molecular ion peak (m/z 694) in the mass spectrum of

(sharp band for OH), 3 070 (broad band for NH), 1 725 (C=O), 1 625 (amide C=O) [similar to acetoacetanilide], 1 600 (NH bending) and 1 520 cm^{-1} (C=C) could be designated according to structures **1** and **2**. Many of the ir bands are also in conformity with those of the parent compound acetoacetanilide.

Scheme 1. Ion reactions of compound **3** in the mass spectrometer.

complex **3** is probably due to thermal instability of the metal chelate in the mass spectrometer. The occurrence of the molecular ion peak for the complex may, however, be well observed from its CI spectra. Mass spectrometric fragmentation of the ligand coming out from the complex produced a good number of intense characteristic peaks (Scheme 1) which speak in favour of the formation of the ligand though not about its binding with molybdenum to form the complex.

The ir spectra of BNA exhibited characteristic bands for both structures **1** as well as **2**. The most intense peaks, appearing at 3 260

The molybdenum complex of BNA showed very intense band at 920 and 892 cm^{-1} (the most characteristic bands⁸ for the two Mo-O₄ bonds with the *cis*-orientation) which are totally absent in the ir spectra of the ligand. The peaks in 3 220 (NH), 1 600 (keto C=O or NH bending), 1 510 (amide C=O) and 1 540 cm^{-1} (C=C) were also rationalised in terms of the structure **3**. The ligand and the complex showed strong bands at 760 (out-of-plane C-H bending vibration)⁹ and 460 cm^{-1} (C-H bending for mono-substituted benzene rings) similar to acetoacetanilide and its molybdenum complex³.

Experimental

The elemental analyses were done using a Carlo-Erba elemental analyser. Ir spectra (KBr) were recorded on a Perkin-Elmer 527 spectrophotometer, mass spectra on DS-55 instrument equipped with a direct inlet system and operating at 70 eV, ¹H nmr spectra (DMSO-*d*₆/CDCl₃) on a Varian EM-390 (90 MHz) instrument and electronic spectra (ethanol) on a Shimadzu UV-160 spectrophotometer. Thermal analysis was done with Al₂O₃ in a photorecording metriplex OD-120 (Hungary) derivatograph. X-Ray powder diffraction was taken in a Phillips (Holland) PW 1729 microprocessor (PW8210) controlled diffractometer. Polarograph LP with line recorder E27 (Czechoslovakia) was used.

Ammonium molybdate and all other chemicals used were of A.R. or G.R. grade. Benzoyl-*m*-nitroacetanilide (BNA) was procured from Dr. J. Das as complementary sample.

Preparation of the molybdenum complex :
To a warm solution of ammonium molybdate

(0.08 g in 10 ml water; pH 1) was added a solution of benzoyl-*m*-nitroacetanilide (2.5 g in 10 ml ethanol) with stirring. The resulting mixture was digested on a water-bath for 15 min and the precipitate was filtered off. The microcrystalline yellow solid was washed successively with water and ethanol, and dried at 110°. The synthesis could be carried out in dilute HCl or H₂SO₄ medium as well. The purity of the complex was further authenticated by tlc studies on silica gel with various solvent systems and the molecular weight was determined by freezing point depression method. The complex was found fairly soluble in acetone but insoluble in most of the organic solvents. It produced molybdenum blue in water above pH 5.0 when kept for long time or quickly when digested on a water-bath (Found : C, 50.05; H, 3.15; N, 8.06; Mo, 13.70. MoO₂(BNA)₂ requires : C, 51.87; H, 3.17; N, 8.07; Mo, 13.83%).

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